

Augmented reality for archaeological finds

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Abstract. Augmented Reality (AR) has become a suitable solution for visualization purposes in several applications such as gaming, entertainment or simple visualization. In contrast, only very few applications considers the use of AR for professional and scientific purposes as their use must be adapted to different applications and specific goals. In this paper, the use of Augmented Reality is applied to archaeological objects visualization. An *ad hoc* cube device and a 3D Studio Max plug-in have been realized for automatically process 3D complex objects models and visualize them with AR open source software. The developed methodology is described in detail and tests on real archaeological objects are reported and commented.

Keywords: Augmented reality, 3D models, visual inspection, archaeology

1 Introduction

In the last decades augmented reality has become a valuable solution for several applications such as gaming, entertainment, education and visualization [1,2]. Augmented reality (AR) can be considered a live, direct or indirect, view of a physical, real-world environment whose elements are augmented (or modified) by computer-generated sensory inputs such as sound, video, graphics or GPS (Global Positioning Systems) data [3]. It differs from virtual reality where the real world is replaced by a simulated one. Augmentation is conventionally in real-time and in semantic context with environmental elements [4]. With the help of advanced AR technology (e.g. adding computer vision and object recognition) an array of archaeological object become interactive and digitally editable while overlain in the real world. Augmented reality examples can be found in very conventional applications, such as sports scores on TV during a match, or in more complex applications, where the artificial information about the environment and its objects can be overlaid on the real world (Figure 1). In recent years the utility of AR for uses beyond entertainment has been realized, for example, by motor company like Toyota, Kia and BMW, which have developed applications that use augmented reality glasses to assist mechanics in performing maintenance on the companies' cars. Currently, there are many iPhone Apps based on AR and Google has started same projects, for example the Project Glass, a research and development program to realize an augmented reality head-mounted display (HMD) [5]. One of the most common AR applications uses tracking recognition to superimpose and track objects on a screen.

Fig. 1. Common application of Augmented reality for on-line shopping and tourism applications

While these types of applications are usually devoted to entertainment, gaming or tourism (Figure 2), their use for scientific use has been limited [6, 7, 8, 9] because they were considered improper for metric and professional use. Another reason AR has not typically been used for scientific purposes is that the necessity to use planar targets in order to load models resulted unsatisfactory in the visualization of complex 3D objects. Because each target allows visualizing object only when it is tilted less than 50° respect to the webcam, higher tilt angles prevent the software to correctly set the target in the space and, as a consequence, the model is not properly visualized on the screen.

This problem is particularly relevant in archaeology where the use of planar targets is only useful to visualize plates and other flat objects; however, more complex objects (such as pots, stones, jewels, etc.) cannot be adequately displayed using a single planar target, because not all of the object sides can be easily visualized.

Fig. 2. Target tracking and superimposition of objects on the screen in different applications

AR devices, however, could be very important for investigating archaeological objects as they provide a non-destructive way for archaeologists, art historians, and other scholars to analyze objects, providing high-resolution details of objects (according to the quality of the acquired 3D model), without the risk to damage, dirty

or alter their color and shape. Moreover, researchers located at diverse locations can simultaneously examine the same objects, thus, facilitating collaboration and enriching archaeological research. However, before such archaeological uses can be realized, a new methodology must be developed that allows all parts of a complex 3D objects to be visualized in a unique model.

In this paper, a new methodology to overcome some of the above mentioned limitations of AR is presented. The methodology uses open-source software and low-cost devices. Several free software and source code are already available on the internet, such as ARSights [10], ArToolkit [11], BuildAR [12], etc. These software toolkits are usually able to manage different models contemporarily: several format files can be managed and the maximum file size depends on the performance of the used PC. Anyway, they usually consider single flat targets and they must be adapted to archaeological applications. First, a new multi-target cube was developed in order to manage all the faces of complex archaeological objects. Second, a *3D Studio Max* plug-in was developed to automatically split the objects into different overlapping faces and load them in an AR software to be visualized. The following sections present the methodology that was developed and then describes first tests on real data to show the potential of this methodology for archaeological research and other scientific fields.

2 3D model generation and pre-processing

The methodology comprises different devices and software that are presented in the following. The description of the multi-target cube and the used AR software is firstly presented. Then, the methodology to preprocess 3D models for AR applications and the description of the 3D Studio Max plug-in to automatically do that are given.

2.1 The multi-target cube and AR open-source software

The cube is composed of six different targets that are visible on each of its faces. Each target loads a different part of the model: each face of the model has to be associated to a defined face of the model in a unequivocal way to correctly reconstruct the object's geometry. Then, the AR software must correctly recognize each target. For this reason, several tests were done to identify the best type of target: the distance of the cube from the webcam were varied, the illumination conditions were changed and different alphanumeric characters were evaluated to determine which of them were able to be recognized without any ambiguity: A, B, C, D, F, and G were chosen, as they assured good results in these tests. The chosen cube size dimension is 8 cm which is a mean value usually suggested by augmented reality software developers. This dimension allows many archaeological objects to be loaded and visualized at a 1:1 scale and assures a sufficient resolution for target recognition at a distance up to 1.5 m from the webcam (with 2 MegaPixels resolution). As already mentioned, while other software exist, BuildAR software (trial version) was used. BuildAR is able to manage several models of thousands of triangles at the same time and can load different file formats.

Fig. 3. The multi-target cube and a screenshot of the BuildAR tool.

Each tile of the whole model is loaded separately into the software and a different target (with the same name) is associated to it. A text file describes the target. The link between faces and model tiles must respect the criteria used in their generation to achieve the correct geometry of the object. In our tests the models were imported in *.obj* file format. While each model can be translated, rotated and scaled, the developed plug-in generates models that can be directly visualized on the screen without the need of any transformation (Figure 3).

2.2 Methodology - Pre-processing of 3D model for Augmented Reality

The proposed methodology is based on different steps. For the sake of simplicity, a sphere is used to explain how the 3D model must be processed for the AR application (Figure 4, left).

Fig. 4. From left to right: the 3D model (i.e. sphere). The test 3D model (sphere) into the multi-target cube. Generation of the intersection pyramid: the base is the cube side, while the vertex in in the cube's center.

The multi-target cube, with the same center of the sphere is virtually reproduced in 3D Studio Max environment: the cube is sized to envelop the test model (in this case the sphere) and each side of the virtual cube is then named in same way as the real

one in order to define an unequivocal association between them (Figure 4, center). A pyramid with its base equal to side and vertex in the cube center (Figure 4, right) is then generated: the same process is repeated for each side of the cube.

Fig. 5. From left to right: Intersection of the pyramids with the simulated 3D model (sphere). Creation of overlapped surfaces between the resulting 3D models through the intersection of overlapped pyramids. Two sub-models given by the intersection of pyramids with the sphere.

Lastly, the test model is intersected by the pyramids and divided into six parts (Figure 5, left). In this way, from a single model, six independent models are generated and the AR software will load each of them separately (according to the associated target). Because not only a slice (i.e. the newly generated sub-models) but the complete 3D model must be visualized in the augmented reality scene, a smooth transition between each sub-model and its adjacent sub-models must be guaranteed, especially when the cube is rotated. For this reason, overlapping pyramids are generally used, increasing the base dimensions (Figure 5, center), and overlapping sub-models are generated (Figure 5, right). Each sub-model is associated with a face on the virtual cube (Figure 6, left) and to its target by a letter (A, B, C, D, F, G); This process allows each sub-model to be loaded separately in the AR software and then visualized (Figure 6 right).

Fig. 6. From left to right: 3D model simulation (sphere) divided in six 3D models. 3D models divided into sub-models, each corresponding to a side of the cube. 3D models visualized in an augmented reality scene.

2.3 3D Studio Max plug-in

Based on the pre-processing requirements described above, an automatic procedure has been developed in order to obtain a 3D model that are directly imported into AR software (i.e. BuildAR). A 3D modeling software program, 3D Studio Max, was chosen to create a simple workflow.

Fig. 7. The MaxScript developed in 3D Studio Max Design 2011

The MaxScript language, natively available to customize 3DS Max Design 2011 was used to create the plug-in because it allows users to create personal windows, buttons, dialogue messages (Figure 7). Before running the plug-in the 3D model is loaded and the export folder is defined. The barycenter of the object is defined to translate the system coordinate origin onto it; a scaling value can be defined if necessary, to scale the object. The shape and the minimum and maximum dimensions are automatically evaluated by the software in order to generate a virtual box sufficient to envelop the whole model and generate pyramids of the correct dimensions. The pyramid size depends on the overlap value defined as input, the vertex is in the center of system coordinate (0,0,0) and the bases parallel to one side of the box. When the overlap is set to zero, each side of the adjacent pyramid is coincident with adjacent pyramid's sides. However, when the overlap is higher, the base of each pyramid will be proportionally bigger than the side of the corresponding box. After the parameters are set and the plug-in is started, the tiles of the models are automatically generated. Each face of the augmented reality software has an independent reference system (X and Y in the target plane and Z coming out this plane). For this reason, each tile is automatically rotated and translated from the 3D model into the new target reference system. Finally the tiles are exported in *.obj* format.

4 Performed tests

In the following section, some tests on different archaeological objects are described. Objects characterized by different shapes, colors and dimensions have been chosen in order to understand the performances, suitability and quality of AR visualization under different operative conditions. The 3D models have dimensions sufficient to “include” the cube during on-screen visualization (the lower dimension is higher than the cube side). The analyzed 3D models were acquired by means of triangulation-based laser scanners. For each artifact, the most adequate geometric resolution was adopted to guarantee a good quality in its visualization: the test models have a sub-millimeter scanning step resolution (0.3 mm). In order to create photo-realistic 3D models, the geometric models were textured with high resolution digital images acquired by a Nikon D3X camera.

4.1 Dalmeri’s Stone

The archaeological object to be tested is a granite stone of irregular shape discovered in the “Riparo Dalmeri”, an archaeological site located in the Trentino region (Italy). Some anthropomorphic figures were painted on its surface about 6000 years ago and they are still visible in ochre. The artifact is about 130 mm high and 60 mm wide and it can be reproduced with AR devices at a 1:1 scale. The 3D model was acquired by using the ShapeGrabber scanner and the complete model (about 300.000 triangles) was divided into 6 overlapping tiles. An overlap of about 20% between adjacent tiles was used in order to guarantee a smooth transition between models when the cube is rotated. In Figure 8, different views, loading one, two and three tiles at the same time are shown: the cube is almost completely wrapped and hidden by the model.

Fig. 8. RD37. AR visualization of the painted stone (RD37) belonging to archaeological paleolithic site “Riparo Dalmeri”, Trento, Italy.

The models looks well defined on the screen because of the high density of polygons in the 3D model and the very high resolution of the images that are used to texture the model. This test shows that the high geometric definition of the model is well reproduced in the augmented reality scene, the boundaries of the stone are sharp, the shape is not simplified and the natural color is well maintained during the visualization.

4.2 Anthropomorphic head

This second test is a anthropomorphic earthenware head and was part of funeral urn. The artifact was found inside an Etruscan tomb (VI century B.C.) and is now located in the Archaeological Etruscan Museum of Chianciano Terme, Italy. The artifact was surveyed using the NextEngine scanner and the final complete 3D model, which comprises about 5 mil. Triangles, was divided into 6 overlapping tiles. The height of the artifact is different from the width and the depth (about 160 mm) dimensions and the overlap between tiles must be sufficient to ensure the complete model reconstruction in every direction.

Fig. 9. Anthropomorphic head of terracotta. Visualization results of the 3D model with standard overlapping.

Fig. 10. Anthropomorphic head of terracotta: AR visualization results with high overlapping between the model tiles.

Several tests were performed in order to define a suitable overlap value between tiles. In Figure 9 the standard overlap values (about the 15%) were used. However, the model looks incomplete in the higher part of the face. Therefore, an overlap of about 40% was used leading to more complete and reliable results (Figure 10).

4.3 Funeral throne of Chianciano Terme

This third test is a Throne that was part of funeral urn (VII century B.C.). The artifact was found inside a tomb and is actually located in the Archaeological Etruscan Museum of Chianciano Terme, Italy.

Fig. 11. AR visualization of an Etruscan throne (part of funeral urn).

The artifact has cylindrical shape and the diameter varies from a minimum of 250 mm in the center to a maximum of 380 mm in the bottom; the height is approximately 440 mm. The survey was carried out using a ShapeGrabber scanner and the complete model comprises about 3 mil. triangles. Due to the elongated shape of the artifact the four pyramids on the horizontal plane were set to have greater overlap than the two pyramids on the vertical axis (top and bottom) to guarantee the complete model reconstruction. This model presents an interesting case because it is convex in the central area. If the standard approach is used, the central part of the model will be inside the cube and it will not be considered in any tile and thus some parts will not be visualized in the final result. To overcome this problem, the vertex of the pyramids was moved in order to guarantee the visibility of the whole model (Figure 11).

5 Conclusions and future developments

In this paper, a new application of augmented reality tools is described and applied to visualize archaeological finds. Compared to already existing applications, the proposed approach allows a complete visualization of complex 3D objects displaying virtual replicas, in real dimensions on screen. The objects can be interactively moved by the operator for a detailed and complete object inspection without any risk of damaging, dirtying or modifying the find. AR tools allow a more direct involvement of the user than traditional modeling software because they allow a real movement of the object without using external devices such as mouse and touchscreen. Single target AR devices are being adopted in museums for visitors. The multi-target cube and the workflow to manage 3D models presented in this paper shows they AR can also be a useful instrument for researchers and archaeologists: the possibility to manage the whole model with a single device and interact with a high definition model on the screen, could be useful for many professional tasks.

The performed tests have provided many useful suggestions for their future use. For example, they have shown that the overlap should be increased according to the object shape and dimensions in order to assure complete model visualization; higher overlaps are usually recommended when stretched objects are considered. Also, in some cases where geometry is very complex (i.e. the Throne) alternative solutions have to be adopted (such as moving the object center or using polygons instead pyramids in the tiling process) to guarantee the visibility of the whole model. The tests also indicated that the target tracking of the cube faces is influenced by the affine

distortions of the target in the webcam image. When the rotation between each target plane and the webcam image plane exceeds 50°, the tracking is not still assured. From this point of view, the use of a polygon composed by only six faces is critical; because a higher number of faces could be difficult for both users and PC to manage. Additionally, the tests indicated that the target tracking of the AR software suffers from illumination conditions: the different illumination between the cube faces can influence the tracking reliability of faces with worse illumination. For this reason, a homogenous indoor illumination of all the faces is suggested. The texture quality of the model partly depends on the illumination and contrast of the screen and the possibility to interactively change the contrast and the illumination of the model.

BuildAR (trial version) has shown its reliability and handiness but unfortunately it does not allow programming and customizations. For this reason, other open-source toolkits will be tested and customized to add some features, such as illumination interactive variation of the model, increasing the completeness of the whole system. The MaxScript developed will be exported to other 3D Modeling software such as Maya and Cinema 4D.

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